

SURVEYING WORKS TO ENSURE THE STABILITY OF SLOPES IN QUARIES

Botirov Shokhbos Soibjon ugli.

TSTU teacher

Tel :+ 998900762471

Email : shoxbos._b@mail.en

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7089911>

Annotation: The calculation of the slope angle, which ensures its stability in the design of open pits, is based on approximate actual initial data. During the operation of the field, numerous factors affecting the stability of the slopes are specified. To prevent possible violations of slope stability, surveyors make systematic instrumental observations.

Keywords: collapse zone, rock mass, stress state, geodetic instruments, profile lines, benchmark, dip.

The depth of many quarries has now reached several hundred meters. The height of overburden dumps in upland quarries sometimes reaches 200 m or more. In this regard, the issues of stability of the slopes of the sides and dumps are among the most relevant for opencast mining, since they are associated with the implementation of measures to ensure the safety of mining operations and improve the technical and economic indicators of the mining enterprise. In particular, an increase in the total wall inclination by only 1° at a pit depth of 300 m leads to a reduction in overburden volume by 3 million m^3 per kilometer of wall length. The calculation of the slope angle, which ensures its stability in the design of open pits, is based on approximate actual initial data.

During the operation of the field, numerous factors affecting the stability of the slopes are specified. To prevent possible violations of slope stability, surveyors make systematic instrumental observations. In case of individual violations, the data of mine surveying observations make it possible to establish the causes and nature of slope stability violations, which are taken into account when adjusting the slope parameters in other sections of the given pit or in other pits with similar conditions. In quarries, the following main types of instability of ledges, sides and dumps are distinguished.

Scree - rolling of individual pieces and blocks to the base of the slope. They are characteristic of all types of rocks, affect the near-surface part of steep slopes and form over several years under the influence of weakening and weathering of rocks on the slope surface.

Collapses capture significant parts of rock masses and occur at slope angles of sides and dumps exceeding $25-35^\circ$, and when weakened layers and disjunctive

disturbances fall towards the excavation at an angle of more than 25–30°. The active stage of collapses proceeds virtually instantly, so they are very dangerous for people and mechanisms working on the underlying ledges.

Landslides - slow displacement of rock masses on a flat surface. They are the most common type of violation of the stability of the sides and dumps. Landslides occur for many reasons, for example , when groundwater flows to a slope, in the presence of layers of plastic clays and pressure waters, with a flooded base and weak rocks in dumps, when the slope angle and its height do not match, etc. The active stage of landslides proceeds during considerable time (from several hours to several months) and involves from hundreds to several million cubic meters of rock mass. Subsidence - vertical lowering of the upper sections of loose rock masses without the formation of a continuous sliding surface. They arise as a result of compaction of waste rocks, their moistening by atmospheric precipitation and consolidation. Subsidence is the least dangerous type of slope instability.

Slumps are characterized by the movement in the form of a flow of sandy-clayey rocks of a disturbed structure (silty sands and clays) saturated with water to a fluid state. They capture significant volumes of rocks, develop intensively, often becoming catastrophic.

Thus, the main factors contributing to the development of slope deformation in quarries are:

- 1) the presence of weakening surfaces - tectonic disturbances, weak contacts between layers, etc.;
- 2) watering of rocks and their weak drainability ;
- 3) intense fracturing of the wall massif;
- 4) the presence of interlayers of flooded clayey rocks.

The main reasons for the development of slope deformation are:

- a) discrepancy between the angles, outlines and heights of slopes given geological conditions, i.e. incorrect calculation of the slope angle;
- b) lack or inefficiency of drainage;
- c) improper conduct of mining operations (mass explosions near the side of the quarry and the sequence of mining sites).

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